

EVOLUTION OF EXPECTATION VIOLATIONS THEORY (EVT) FROM FACE-TO FACE COMMUNICATION ON COMPUTER-MEDIATED COMMUNICATION: (CASE STUDY OF INDONESIA HOLYWINGS PROMOTION)

CATUR SURATNOAJI

University of Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia.

SYIFA SYARIFAH ALAMIYAH

University of Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia.

MADE HANINDA PRAMI SWARI

University of Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia.

TRESNA MAULANA FAHRUDIN

University of Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia.

AMALIA ANJANI ARIFIYANTI

University of Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia.

Abstract

The promotion carried out by Holywings in the religious community is a promotional strategy that carries a big risk considering that the majority of Indonesian people are Muslims where liquor is an unlawful item. This was considered a violation and sparked various reactions in society. In the digital era, data sourced from social media is important data to understand the response of the Indonesian people to the violation of the Holywings issue. The research method used is explorative because marketing communication research based on social media data is still new. The research method is descriptive and quantitative by describing variables such as user volume, reach, conversation trends, top tweets, sentiments, influencers, and communication networks between social media users. The research sample uses the period from 23 June 2022 to 30 June 2022. The results of this research indicate that the issue of the Holywings violation is viral compared to other issues. The scope of the issue of violations at Café Holywings spreads throughout Indonesia and is dominant in DKI Jakarta Province. Even though Bali is the biggest branch of Café Holywings, there was very little reaction to the violation of Café Holywings. This is following the theory of expectation violations that the size of the violation reaction on social media is highly dependent on individual characteristics, context, and reaction.

Keywords: Big Data, Social Media, Expectation Violation Theory, Holywings.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian people were shocked by the promotional strategy used by Holywings. The promotion is spread through the social media platform Instagram @holywingsbar which has around 46 thousand followers. In the story post for the account, there is an inscription indicating that they will provide free alcohol for visitors who have the name Muhammad or Maria in their full name. Free alcohol will be given every Thursday. Visitors bearing Muhammad's name will receive a bottle of Gordon's dry gin and those bearing Maria's name will receive a bottle of Gordon's Pink.

The promotion carried out by Holywings in the religious community is a promotional strategy that carries a big risk considering that the majority of Indonesian people are Muslims where liquor is an unlawful item. Changing people's beliefs from something that was "unlawful" to "halal" is an impossible job, although it can happen. The problem is not the effectiveness of the promotion strategy but the use of the names Muhammad or Maria which are considered offensive to Muslim and Christian communities. Every promotion strategy should understand the ethical boundaries in marketing communication in the business world. Anyone, in any case, to avoid playing with SARA issues because it can trigger a public reaction. In addition, the promotional actions of Hollywings can be considered a form of violation of Law no. 11 of 2008 concerning Information and Electronic Transactions (UU ITE). In the ITE Law, Article 28 paragraph 2 reads "Every person purposefully and without rights disseminates information to instill hatred or enmity towards specific individuals and/or groups of people based on ethnicity, religion, race, and inter-group (SARA). The goal of this essay is to prevent confrontations, riots, or even divides based on SARA from occurring as a result of inflammatory lousy information. According to the religious community, the SARA issue is highly sensitive. As a result, this article is governed by formal offenses rather than material offenses.

The promotion strategy carried out by Hollywings can be categorized as a violation of the expectations of the Muslim and Christian communities. It is said to be a violation because the promotional content of Hollywings is against the ITE Law. After all, it is considered to be offensive to certain religions. In the context of communication, if one communication participant commits a violation or behaves not following cultural norms, the other participants will be offended, and angry, and this can cause conflict. This is following Judee Burgoon's Expectation Violation Theory (1978), where each communication participant is required to communicate (both verbal and non-verbal) following prevailing norms and culture (Burgoon et al., 2016). The Expectation Violation Theory initially developed in the form of interpersonal communication, but with the development of communication and information technology, this theory can be expanded in the form of internet-mediated communication such as social media.

The study of the ethics of using social media in the digital era continues to gain great popularity. The rapid advances in information and communication technology have made it easier for users to communicate, share and exchange information, and make it easier to promote social and political activities (Beer, 2008, Boyd, Danah, Ellison, 2007, (Claure et al., 2020) Brody, 2021). A critical question related to digital communication is whether the interpersonal communication theory developed based on face-to-face communication can be applied to computer-mediated research such as social media. To answer this, researchers must analyze one premise, including: "Who are the social media friends you communicate with the most? While social media conveys an impression of anonymity, most of its networks are made up of individuals who do not know each other as face-to-face communication does. Boyd and Ellison (2007) also point out that although people may use social media to make connections with people they have never met in person, that is often not the goal... part of their extended social network (Boyd, Danah, Ellison, 2007). Dunbar (2016) expressed an opinion that people also have cognitive constraints

in maintaining online social networks. To maintain stable online relationships, people also need to see each other in person. These results indicate that the concepts of interpersonal communication will likely experience problems when used as a reference to explain internet-based digital communication activities (Fife et al., 2012). In the context of the theory of implementation of the Expectancy Violation Theory in social media, most communicators are acquaintances in face-to-face communication. Therefore, the reality of interpersonal communication can be considered similar to understanding communication activities in the online world or social media. Referring to these arguments, interpersonal communication measures can be developed to understand the use of the Expectancy Violation Theory in the social media domain (Bennett & Tikkanen, 2020).

The use of social media as any activity requires ethics so that there is no violation of expectations. Ethics is a set of values applied in the digital world. Although communication takes place in the virtual world and social media platforms are often limited in text and images, there is a need for standardized rules based on the rules of interpersonal communication just as they do in the real world. Ethics is a standard rule that must be owned by everyone when entering a social network or virtual world community. Several reasons must be based on ethics in the digital world, including 1) First, digital media users are not equal and come from the same environment. The large number of users who are in digital media, the user's backgrounds, and cultural diversity have opened up opportunities for conflict or hostility. 2) Communication that occurs in digital media tends to rely solely on text. Of course, there is the possibility of analyzing the text alone in this circumstance. Of course, there is a possibility of text interpretation between the user who produces the text and the user who gets the information in this circumstance. This difference is related to culture. 3) Digital media content is not only directed to the desired user but can occur indirectly. Computer-mediated communication is of course not limited to communication involving only two people, but also at a much broader level of communication. 4) Digital media is not necessarily considered a different medium and separate from the real world. 5) The ethics of using digital media is necessary so that every user in the virtual world understands his rights and obligations as a "citizen" of the virtual world ((Rully Nasrullah, 2022)

The purpose of this study is to determine whether patterns of interpersonal communication behavior on social media can be explained and interpreted using the framework of the Expectation Violation Theory (EVT). This inquiry leads to a number of distinct topics. At this point, how vital are EVT concepts and predictions to interpersonal connection on social media when receiving Café Holywings promotional messages? Second, what are the characteristics of communication valence (i.e., expectation valence, expectation violation, communicator valence, behavior valence, and violation and violation effect) in computer-mediated or social media communication compared to face-to-face communication, and the resulting impact on evaluation and Interpersonal interaction also determines the response to the violation? Although the promotion of liquor is considered a violation of public expectations, the reaction is not necessarily negative, perhaps there is also a positive one. According to Judee Burgoon's Theory of Violating

Expectations, when a person deviates from expectations, and how that deviation is accepted or rejected by the audience, the subject is determined by the potential benefits and repercussions from other individuals. Burgoon, Deborah Coker, and Ray Coker (1986) observed that not all breaches of expected behavior lead to negative perceptions (Bevan et al., 2014).

Proof of the Expectation Violation Theory or EVT on social media is often still a discourse and has not been proven. This is because there are obstacles to understanding the reactions or responses of social media users in downloading and analyzing them. This study uses a big data-based research method approach because it is difficult to use a survey approach to analyze hidden text, images, and videos in the virtual world. It is possible that a survey approach was used but could not fully capture what happened in the virtual world when the Café Hollywings liquor promotion was launched. Big Data is not a technology, technique, or initiative that stands alone. Big Data is a trend that covers a wide area in the world of business and technology (Suratnoaji, 2021). Big Data refers to technologies and initiatives that involve data that is so diverse, rapidly changing, or supersized that it is too difficult for conventional technology, expertise, or infrastructure to handle it effectively. In other words, Big Data has a size (volume), velocity (velocity), or variety that is too extreme to be managed with conventional techniques. Big Data involves processes of data creation, storage, information extraction, and analysis that stand out in terms of volume, velocity, and variety. Data and business seem to be a complete package, the two cannot be separated. As a business that operates in the technological era, of course, complete data with analysis is the most important part that can support policy direction in running a business. Complete data analysis is no longer just an important competency for corporate organizations, but as a determinant of market dominance and used as a reference basis for where the business will run and develop. Some of the benefits of Big Data that have been felt, particularly in the business world, including knowing the public's response to products issued through sentiment analysis on social media, collaborating with companies to execute more precise and accurate data-driven decisions, and assisting companies in improving their image in the eyes of customers for business planning by understanding customer behavior.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The Expectancy Violations Theory (EVT) is an interpersonal communication theory that interprets how individuals respond to unexpected violations of social norms and expectations. According to Burgoon (1978), there are two types of violations: violations of norms and violations of expectations. The first violation refers to the violation of social rules in a particular community where the conversation takes place, while the second violation refers to the behavior of a particular communicator against existing cognition or prior knowledge about the communicator himself. Violation of expectations can have positive and negative valence, one example of positive valence is someone has praised your post on social media, and an example of negative valence is when someone gives a negative comment on your post. It should be added that most violations of the norms expected in an act of communication are viewed as negative (Burgoon et al., 2016).

Furthermore, another communicative valence, behavioral valence, and environmental elements, according to EVT, are engaged in the process of interpersonal evaluation and subsequent action. In other words, when expectations are violated, the violation will be regarded as positive or negative, acceptable or undesirable, substantial or trivial (Reward value) based on the closeness of the relationship and the profitability and relevance of the violation. Perceived (Johnson & Lewis, 2010). Determining the amount of this prize can have an impact on the understanding of the violation, ambiguous behavior, and the reactions of those who engage in the violation (Fife et al., 2012). In line with, interpretation leads to substantial responses, which can be communicative or internal reactions. Although expectancy violation theory was originally developed to analyze individual expectations of personal distance and how responses to this distance violation are influenced by the level of preference for and affinity for the behavior (Burgoon & Jones, 1976), it is currently used to interpret violations in a wide range of nonverbal communication contexts and verbal (Bennett & Tikkanen, 2020). For example, this approach is applied to nonverbal communication in the form of intimacy and touch behaviors by Burgoon and colleagues (1988, 1992). EVT has also been extended by other researchers to interpret behavior in close relationships (Bevan et al., 2014), teaching and learning contexts (Stutzman & Kramer-Duffield, 2010), occupation contexts (Johnson & Lewis, 2010), and public health campaign issues (Shi, 2014).

EVT has been developed in the context of computer-mediated communication in the past few decades. However, to the finest of the researcher's knowledge, this issue has not been properly investigated and established by analysis of social media data. Thus, this study tries to apply EVT in the use of social media as a means of communication with the communication network analysis method. Communication network analysis will investigate communication networks between social media users alongside their reactions when social and cultural standards are violated.

2.1. Online Social Norms and Violation of Expectations

Customs, traditions, standards, regulations, values, fashions, and all other behavioral characteristics that are standardized as a consequence of individual contact are examples of social norms. In other words, social norms are standards by which people determine whether or not certain behaviors are proper. Although social norms frequently evolve with IT technology in the online setting, numerous investigations have demonstrated that offline norms also apply in online contexts, even when users remain anonymous (Sloan et al., 2017). McLaughlin and Vitak (2011) discovered that offline civility standards are identically relevant in online encounters. In this regard, he draws the conclusion that if offline standards operate effectively in anonymous online background information, they should have a bigger influence on behavior on social media, where user identification is not immediately apparent (McLaughlin et al., 2011).

However, other scholars (e.g. (Boyd, Danah, Ellison, 2007) also argue that the norms governing interactions on social media such as Facebook must be different from the norms governing offline interactions. In general, this theoretical framework follows that of Cohen (2010) which differentiates online norms as moral norms, belief norms, and social

norms. Therefore, previous research indicates that moral transgressions (e.g., abusive behavior, aggression, sexual desire) deviating), breach of trust (e.g., betrayal of trust, deception) and social misconduct (e.g., disrespectful, unfriendly, belittling) can have adversarial consequences for close relationships both offline and online on social media (Cohen, 2010).

(McLaughlin et al., 2011) promoted discussions about social media guidelines among several groups of students. Although there are different etiquette guidelines available, individuals tend to construct and follow unspoken or implicit conventions inside any online organization. According to MacLaughlin and Vitak (2011), too many unimportant and disruptive updates, as well as status updates or very sentimental public posts, were perceived as a violation of expectations. In addition, rejecting or ignoring friend requests from someone they have met in person, or unfriending friends on social media is considered a very negative expectation violation (Bevan et al., 2014). Furthermore, failing to differentiate between public and private interactions, such as heated interactions, confrontations, name-calling on social media, and intrusive surveillance, are seen negatively (Fife et al., 2012). Tagging a friend's photo, or virtually any kind of wall post that has the potential to adversely affect social media friends' self-presentation, giving an unfavorable impression, is also perceived as a violation of negative expectations (Fife et al., 2012).

While most of the responses regarding the breach of expectations have been negative, we believe there may also be some positive ones through our interactions on social media. According to MacLaughlin & Vitak, potential violations of positive expectations may take the form of reinforcing weak bonds, exemplified by receiving messages or tagging pictures by childhood friends can lead to reunions. Violation of expectations can also enhance existing close relationships, such as taking advice from a father who hardly ever speaks directly to his children (McLaughlin et al., 2011).

2.2. Characteristics of EVT in the context of SNS

Technological breakthroughs in computer-mediated communications over the Internet have resulted in the continual growth of social norms and standards. MacLaughlin and Vitak (2011), for example, conducted a series of exploratory studies on the research question of how norms of individual behavior change over time and discovered that people constantly change their profiles over time, including updating their privacy settings when posts or tweets have consequences. Unfavorable by omitting some essential elements from their personal information. Following the development of the self-presentation stage theory (McLaughlin & Vitak, 2012), they identify this context collapse phenomenon. In contrast to face-to-face communication situations, each interaction context remains relatively separate. As a consequence, people possibly immediately determine how to act and portray themselves. However, social circles are constantly increasing in the context of online communication via social media, which may inspire individuals to alter their self-presentation on Social Networking Sites (SNS). As a consequence, self-presentation necessitates ongoing maintenance, requiring users to adapt their social media network practices to the times (for example, socializing and

sharing information). Experts additionally indicate that social standards on social media fluctuate with age, such as Dimicco and Millen (2007), who discovered that older age groups (with more prolonged occupation experience) tend to publish less personal information, but more information directed to their profession. Profile. Similarly, McLaughlin and Vitak (2011) proposed that Facebook users of various generations utilize the platform for different objectives according to distinct norms (McLaughlin et al., 2011).

The situations that occur when a communicator who is not rewarding or who has a negative valence erroneously violates expectations, the behaviour in question ought to be commended; on the other hand, a poor offence committed by a communicator who is rewarding or who has a positive valence will result in compensation. McLaughlin and Vitak (2011) discovered that on Facebook, reactions to positive offences are consistent with the predictions of Expectancy Violation Theory. On the other hand, negative norm violations produce responses that deviate from the predictions of Expectancy Violation Theory. Recent research on social media networks, however, contradicts the predictions of classic Expectancy Violation Theory. Other situations of expectation violations illustrate that people are more inclined to respond with a confrontational response to close friends and a compensatory response to casual acquaintances. This observation contradicts Expectancy Violation Theory's expectations.

Previous research has revealed three distinct intermediate expectation violations. First, an invasion of privacy, particularly by strangers or casual acquaintances, will be regarded as a breach of standard expectations. Thematic analysis of group conversation transcripts was performed by the Fife research team (2012). They emphasize that "stalking personal information and social activities via social media and "gossiping" are highly regarded as an infringement of unfavorable expectations. He also demonstrated that the breach of expectations of privacy infringement by weak bonds along with increased interpersonal privacy concerns could potentially lead to privacy-enhancing behaviors, such as creating profiles that only close friends can access (Fife et al., 2012).

Second, questioning one's self-presentation goals is an infringement of certain expectations. According to Walther et al. (2008), a person's social media profile and other public posts customize the audience's perception of them. In context collapse contexts (for example, Facebook), social media friends such as close friends, family, colleagues, and maybe even non-friends would be able to comprehend the information at the same time. As a consequence, unexpected engagement behaviors such as angry confrontations, arguments, and name-calling on social media are likely to place a person's suitable image in jeopardy. For example, Walther et al. (2008) reported that inappropriate messages about certain moral behaviors (eg, drinking heavily, having promiscuous sex, or uttering obscenities) increased the male profile owner's perception of physical attractiveness, whereas that of women decreased perceived attractiveness. To avoid or reduce potential damage to one's self-presentation goals, social media users will delete offenders or create friends-only accounts (Stutzman & Kramer-Duffield, 2008)(McLaughlin et al., 2011). Third, (Ramirez & Wang, 2008) also explores the occurrence of modality switching (MS) from the perspective of expectation violation

theory, in which they consider social information provided through modality switching MS (virtual computer-mediated communication-mediated shift (CMC) to face-to-face interaction). (Face to face). Be an exception to the rule. Previous research has demonstrated that modality switching (MS) can have an impact on communicator perception, social appraisal, and future relationship growth in ways that are both beneficial and detrimental. They emphasize, in particular, that participants in the offending condition view information more favorably and as more important than participants in the non-modality switching (MS) condition. They also investigated the time-moderating effect of modality switching (MS). The results show that switching to face-to-face interaction after short-term online communication will not only make communicators evaluate their partner more positive, but also reduces the sense of uncertainty in their relationship (McLaughlin et al., 2011).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses big data research methods that optimize social media data as analytical data. This type of research is still exploratory in nature, where this research is an exploration of a topic or phenomenon in the world of digital marketing communications. Due to their exploratory nature, these studies are generally not deep. The novelty of the methods and perspectives that have never been done before determines the significance of an exploratory study (Collector & Module, 2011). The analysis of communication networks between social media users in discussing controversial issues regarding the inclusion of the name Muhammad - Maria in emotional promos at Café Holywings is directed towards the measurement of Indonesian people's engagement with the Café Holywings promo. Several research concepts related to the analysis of the engagement of the Indonesian people on issues include several variables, including: 1) Degree centrality or opinion leader as measured by the number of connections Twitter users have when discussing certain issues. 2) The topic of discussion that is most discussed by social media users regarding the violation of Café Holywings 3) the centrality of intermediaries as measured by a person's position when dealing with other actors in a communication network on social media. 4) Eigenvector centrality is a measure of how influential people with connections to actors examine the Café Holywings infringement. 5) The clustering coefficient computes the proportion of connectivity among a particular number of social media users (Hansen et al., 2011). As an effort to measure these variables, researchers use NodeXL software to download, process and analyze data on social media.

The unit of analysis in this study is the relationship between social media users formed by discussing the issue of violations at Café Holywings. To download data related to the Café Holywings violation, researchers used the keyword "Holywings" to download Twitter data. The researcher downloaded data on the Twitter media platform from 23 June 2022 to 30 June 2022. This timeframe has been selected in recognition of the realisation that Café Holywings first issued the campaign according to the name "Muhammad-Maria" on June 23, 2022. The decision-making procedure of social media Twitter became another focus of investigation as a consequence of Facebook and Instagram regulations that have restricted public access to data after the Facebook and Cambridge Analytica scandals in

2017. For the sake of preventing such difficulties in future periods, Facebook implemented adjustments to its services, including the closure of Facebook and Instagram data to the general public. Twitter and online media are the only remaining sources of social media data.

The analytical method of studying the theory of expectation violations in the Holywing Café violation case uses three levels of analysis, including: a). Media analysis that places more emphasis on the reach, engagement, and virality aspects of the issue of Café Holywings violations. b). Conversation analysis (conversation analysis) seeks to understand the words most used by social media users. In addition, this study also measures public response sentiment regarding Café Holywings' budgeting. c). Network analysis (network analysis) focused on who spoke with whom, what was discussed, who were the people who had high influence (influencers) in a communication network of Café Holywings violations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indonesia has a religious society and, all citizens hope that one another respects and respects one another. It is an expectation that encourages everyone to interact with various cultures to create a harmonious society. When there is a promotional message for Café Holywings liquor using the name "Muhammad-Maria" on June 23, 2022, this is considered a violation or deviation in the religious community. Liquor for the Muslim community is a forbidden drink and the law is prohibited to drink. Café Holywing made a promo containing an invitation to the Muslim community to violate religious norms and this is a violation. According to Judee Burgoon (1978), every deviation from expectations has consequences. These deviations or violations have what is referred to as a "stimulus value". That is, when a person's expectations are violated, a person's interest or attention will be stimulated so that he will use certain mechanisms to deal with the violation that occurs. When stimulation (arousal) occurs, one's interest or attention to deviation will increase and attention to the message will decrease while attention to the source of the stimulus will increase (Burgoon in West, 2008).

a. Twitter Social Media User Volume

The violations committed by Café Holywings aroused public reaction to Café Holywing's promo messages. This can be seen from the span of one week (23 June to 30 June 2022), there were 10,779 social media user accounts discussing the Holywing case and 21,653 interactions were created between Twitter media users. Forms of interaction between Twitter users are mostly created through 14,731 retweets, 2,775 tweets, 2,182 mentions in tweets, 1140 dependent to 1140, and 1140 mentions. Able to generate public attention and emotion towards the issue. This shows that the Holywings issue is a sensitive issue that has disturbed the harmonization of religious communities, especially Muslim and Christian communities. The number of social media users discussing Holywings violation messages is 10,770. Within one week, this number beat other issues in Indonesia. The large volume of Twitter social media users shows that the Café Holywing promo is a serious violation. Serious violations on social media will trigger an

audience response. In contrast to violations that are categorized as low, they do not generate much public reaction. The virality of an issue on social media can occur due to two aspects, viral because of someone's kindness or success and viral because of someone's bad luck. Most of the Indonesian people's responses to Holywing's violations were in the form of "Retweet" at 68%, "Tweet" at 13%, "MentionsInRetweet" at 10%, and "Replies To" at 5%. Retweet is reposting a Tweet. The Retweet feature on Twitter helps social media users share those tweets with all their followers. Retweets by Twitter social media users act to expand the message of Holywings or are an "amplification" of messages to other users. In detail, the response of Twitter users to the Holywings promo can be seen as follows:

Figure 1: Types of User Reactions to the Holywings Issue

b. Trends on the Holywings Issue

The trend of discussing the Holywings issue from time to time continues to increase due to the interactive and widely connected nature of social media with other users of mine. The increasing existence of social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Youtube, Tik Tok and so on has made it easier for social media users to interact with each other in discussing the issue of Holidays. Internet-based connected social media is not just a medium that mediates the process of message distribution and circulation, but as a medium like an environment in face-to-face communication. Social media provides a means to arouse audience interest and shape public opinion on certain issues such as Holywings. Although the first publication of the Café Holywings promo was on June 23, 2022, the crystallization of public opinion was only formed stably on June 28, 2022. The crystallization of public opinion formed through social media shows that social media is very effective in generating stimulation of interest in people who feel disturbed about promo Café Holywings. This can be seen in the following graph.

Figure 2: Holywings Conversation Trends on Twitter Social Media

c. Holywings issue reach

In addition to the trend of discussing the Holywings issue, an analysis of the response of the Indonesian people to the Holywings issue can be seen from the range of promo issues that use the name "Muhammad-Maria" in Indonesia. The distribution of issues is important to see which areas are very dominant in reacting to the "Muhammad-Maria" issue considering that Holywings Café is in various regions in Indonesia such as Jakarta, Semarang, Bandung, Surabaya, Medan, Bali, and others. Although Holywings branches exist in various cities in Indonesia, it turns out that the biggest reaction or response from the community is still on the island of Java. Based on the analysis of social media data, it shows that there are 2677 locations used by social media users in responding to the Holywings case. The top 5 social media users mostly come from the cities of Jakarta, Bandung, Yogyakarta, Surabaya, and Semarang. The interesting thing in this research is the lack of response from Twitter social media users who come from the city of Bali even though the Holywing branch in the Canggu area of Bali is the largest branch among other branches. This can be seen in the following distribution of response locations.

Figure 3: Coverage of "Holywings" Issues in Indonesia

According to Figure 3, the majority of Indonesians' reactions to the discussion of "Holywings" were from DKI Jakarta Province (35%), West Java (15%), Yogyakarta (8%), East Java (6%), Central Java (4%), Bali (1%), and other provinces (26%). The popular reaction to the subject of "Holywings" is concentrated on the island of Java, particularly in DKI Jakarta, West Java, and East Java. This is important to understand because the island of Java has a Muslim majority. Although the virtual world is not restricted by existence or time, the proximity or proximity of the center of power has profoundly influenced the public's behavior towards the discussion of "Holywings," as well as recognizing that the majority of Holywings branches are on the island of Java. Psychologically, accounts that are in the center of power and also close to the Holywings branches can pressure power holders to pay attention to the "Holywings" issue. If the channeling of aspirations through social media has not shaken the rulers, then the down-the-road movement will be the last alternative. The function of social media is essentially a means of mobilizing social media users to be interested in discussing the issue of "Holywings" and can be a force for the authorities to take action to close Café Holywings. The Balinese response is extremely limited considering the Balinese follow Hinduism and are not immediately touched by the Holywings promotional message that uses the name "Muhammad-Maria". According to Judee Burgoon (1978), individual characteristics such as gender, age, personality, religion, and social and culture determine the response or reaction to violations committed by communicators (Burgoon in West, 2008).

d. Top Tweets on "Holywings" Issue

To discover the Indonesian population's reaction to the "Holywings" issue, examine the contents of the discussion as well as the objections to what was discussed. Many elements influence the type of community reaction to the "Holywings" issue, including individual, relational, and contextual components. According to Burgoon, individual factors include gender, religion, age, personality, etc. Relational factors include the history of the underlying relationship, differences in status, level of interest, and like. Context factors include formality/informality, task function, environmental boundaries, and socio-culture. The diagram below shows the discussion on the issue of "Holywings" which received the most responses from other users.

Figure 4: Top Twett Discussing the Issue of "Holywings"

Based on Figure 4, shows that the tweet that received the most responses from social media users came from the @hendrypri account. The Tweet is negative which tends not to tolerate violations committed by Café Holywings. Tweets submitted by the @hendrypri account tend to disagree with the violations of Café Holywings and also disagree with the person responsible.

"So I remember the blunder case of the social media team and the legal issue of Eiger. Those who apologized put on their bodies, and admitted they were wrong, in public, directly to the CEO. Get a lot of respect, and the case is closed. Holywings hello?"

The tweet is a form of negative social media user reaction because it is aimed at the Holywings violation but focuses more on the person responsible for the violation. This tweet received a lot of responses because social media users questioned the legal responsibility imposed on the creative team for the Holywings promo, the leadership managing Holywings should also be responsible. This is like the incident in the Eiger company case in 2021 where Eiger's leaders or CEOs are responsible for cases caused by their subordinates. Some believe that the Holywings promotion is not a violation, as indicated in a retweet by the @indonesiatren account that "The Holywing Case is Not a Legal Issue". Another response that considers it not a violation and that Holywing needs to be forgiven comes from the following @rsdnet account.

"The Holywings case is not just a matter of law, it is about; the fate of 3,000 employees of Holywings, the recklessness of Holywings & the cunning A.R."

e. Holywings Issue Sentiment

Social media user engagement can be negative or positive towards violations of the Holywings promo, depending on individual and socio-cultural characteristics. However, the reactions of media users who were negative (71%) were far more dominant than those who were positive (5%) and those who were neutral (24%), as shown in the following data.

Figure 5: Sentiment on the Holywings Issue

Figure 6 shows that the @knpiharis account is the top influencer. In the real world, the @knpiharis account is the first Haris who is also the general chairman of the KNPI DPP for the 2018-2021 period, after he was elected at the XV Congress. Haris Pertama is also known as an activist from the Islamic Student Association (HMI) as well as chairman of the NKRI Guard which he founded in 2007. Haris Pertama is known as a critical person and often criticizes government policies, both regarding law and environmental issues. In the case of Holywings, it shows that Haris Pertama besides acting as a "top influencer" also acts as a "betweenness" that bridges citizens who object and the rulers of the Republic of Indonesia such as @jokowi (President of the Republic of Indonesia) and @listyosigitp (Kapolri). The role of the @knpiharis account is trying to suppress the existence of a bigger conflict among the Indonesian people.

Figure 6: Holywings. Issue Communication Network

4. CONCLUSION

The issue of discussing alcohol promo violations that include the name "Muhammad-Maria" on social media is much-discussed in the period from 23 June 2022 to 30 June 2022. This issue is growing rapidly because it is considered a violation of promo content that invites Muslims and Christians to buy liquor, even though this product is forbidden to drink. The Holywings issue does not spread throughout Indonesia, but only on the island of Java, especially in the provinces of DKI Jakarta, West Java, Yogyakarta, East Java, and Central Java. The discussion on the Holywings issue gave a negative reaction because the issue was considered to have defamed or insulted Muslim and Christian groups. Most of the community responses on social media do not tolerate violations of the Holywings issue. Only a small portion of society tolerates abuse out of pity for the plight of the 3,000 employees of Holywings. The @knpiharis account acts as a top

influencer because it has a big role in voicing the movement to reject the Café Holywings promo.

Suggestion to the Society

The findings of the research conducted on the promotion instances involving Holywings can serve as a reference for businesses, who can use it to remind them to always pay attention to ethics and community norms when they are marketing. It is possible for infractions of ethical and societal standards committed by social media material to cause damage to the reputation of the product image and even lead to consumer boycotts of the product. The findings of this research are also very helpful for the community to gain skills in digital literacy in order to deal with communications that break the rules and ethics of the community. When there are violations associated to ethnicity, people are able to stop themselves from becoming hostile towards one another, participating in rioting, or even dividing themselves due to negative information that provokes them. The Indonesian society does not engage in acts of anarchy or cyberbullying against Holywings on social media; rather, it places its faith in the ability of law enforcement personnel to resolve incidents involving Holywings violations.

References

- 1) Beer, D. (2008). Social network(ing) sites...revisiting the story so far: A response to danah boyd & Nicole Ellison. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2008.00408.x>
- 2) Bennett, L. K., & Tikkanen, S. A. (2020). Teaching expectancy violations theory and self-disclosure through social media profile building. *Communication Teacher*, 34(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17404622.2019.1662070>
- 3) Bevan, J. L., Ang, P. C., & Fearn, J. B. (2014). Being unfriended on Facebook: An application of Expectancy Violation Theory. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.01.029>
- 4) Boyd, Danah, Ellison, N. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1).
- 5) Brody, N. (2021). Bystander Intervention in Cyberbullying and Online Harassment: The Role of Expectancy Violations. *International Journal of Communication*, 15.
- 6) Burgoon, J. K., Bonito, J. A., Lowry, P. B., Humpherys, S. L., Moody, G. D., Gaskin, J. E., & Giboney, J. S. (2016). Application of Expectancy Violations Theory to communication with and judgments about embodied agents during a decision-making task. *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, 91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2016.02.002>
- 7) Burgoon, J. K., & Jones, S. B. (1976). Toward A Theory of Personal Space Expectations and Their Violations. *Human Communication Research*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.1976.tb00706.x>
- 8) Claire, H., Khojasteh, N., Tennent, H., & Jung, M. (2020). Using expectancy violations theory to understand robot touch interpretation. *ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3371382.3378314>
- 9) Cohen, E. L. (2010). Expectancy violations in relationships with friends and media figures. *Communication Research Reports*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08824091003737836>

- 10) Collector, D., & Module, F. G. (2011). Qualitative Research Methods Overview. Qualitative Research Methods A Data Collectors Field Guide. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3172595>
- 11) Dimicco, J. M., & Millen, D. R. (2007). Identity management: Multiple presentations of self in facebook. GROUP'07 - Proceedings of the 2007 International ACM Conference on Supporting Group Work. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1316624.1316682>
- 12) Fife, E., Nelson, C. L., & Zhang, K. (2012). A New Horizon for a Classic Perspective: Facebook and Expectancy Violation Theory. *Journal of the Communication, Speech & Theatre Association of North Dakota*, 25.
- 13) Hansen, D. L., Shneiderman, B., & Smith, M. A. (2011). Analyzing Social Media Networks With NodeXL. In *Analyzing Social Media Networks with NodeXL*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2009-0-64028-9>
- 14) Johnson, D. I., & Lewis, N. (2010). Perceptions of swearing in the work setting: An expectancy violations theory perspective. *Communication Reports*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08934215.2010.511401>
- 15) McLaughlin, C., & Vitak, J. (2012). Norm evolution and violation on facebook. *New Media and Society*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444811412712>
- 16) McLaughlin, C., Vitak, J., & Crouse, J. (2011). Online identity construction and expectation of future interaction. *Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2011.329>
- 17) Ramirez, A., & Wang, Z. (2008). When online meets offline: An expectancy violations theory perspective on modality switching. *Journal of Communication*, 58(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2007.00372.x>
- 18) Rully Nasrullah. (2022). *Teori Dan Riset Media Siber (Cybermedia)*.
- 19) Shi, L. (2014). Micro-blogs, Online Forums, and the Birth-Control Policy: Social Media and the Politics of Reproduction in China. *Culture, Medicine and Psychiatry*, 38(1), 115–132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11013-013-9351-x>
- 20) Sloan, L., Quan-Haase, A., & Beninger, K. (2017). Social Media Users' Views on the Ethics of Social Media Research. In *The SAGE Handbook of Social Media Research Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473983847.n5>
- 21) Stutzman, F., & Kramer-Duffield, J. (2008). Modeling cultural acquisition in online social networks. *Proceedings of the ASIST Annual Meeting*, 45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/meet.2008.14504503148>
- 22) Stutzman, F., & Kramer-Duffield, J. (2010). Friends only: Examining a privacy-enhancing behavior in facebook. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1753326.1753559>
- 23) Suratnoaji, C. and I. D. A. (2021). *Metode Riset Sosial Berbasis Big Data*.
- 24) Walther, J. B., van der Heide, B., Kim, S. Y., Westerman, D., & Tong, S. T. (2008). The role of friends' appearance and behavior on evaluations of individuals on facebook: Are we known by the company we keep? *Human Communication Research*, 34(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.2007.00312.x>